

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Here is the final issue of J.UCS of the year 2002 - with a total of more than 1000 published pages, we look back on yet another successful year. Also the printed annual volume will appear within a few weeks - do not forget to ask your library to order it if you haven't done so already (see http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription/print.html).

I would like to thank all of you for your contributions, your help in reviewing, and your continuous support of J.UCS. With a number of new submissions and special issues already in waiting I can assure you that 2003 will be another good year for our journal. Please do help to spread the message!

All the best for 2003 on behalf of all the members of the editorial staff of J.UCS (and with a big "Thanks" to my editorial assistant Dana Kaiser)!

Cordially,

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